

COVID^X

THE GAME CHANGERS

WELCOME BROCHURE

For COVID-X Solutions
Open Call #2
November 2021

Welcome to the COVID-X Programme!

The entire COVID-X Project Team is very happy that your solution & team joined the COVID-X Community, and we will be working together for the next ten months until September 2022!

To get you ready for the COVID-X journey, we have gathered some useful information regarding:

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KICK-OFF BOOTCAMP

To present you the COVID-X Journey, teams & selected solutions, you are invited to take part in the kick-off Bootcamp!

Date & Time: on Friday, the 26th of November 2021, at 12:00 CET

During the online Bootcamp you will meet the COVID-X team and all successful solutions from the Open Call#2. **Get prepared to give a 3-minutes pitch** about your project & solution! Book the meeting slot now and notice that the meeting access link and agenda will be communicated by mail closer to the event.

To prepare your pitch (3 slides max), please feel free to use the COVID-X slide deck template available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Light_presentation_template

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

All internal communication takes place in two dedicated channels:

Mailing list: covid-x-oc2-solutions@f6s.com - subscription to the mailing list is mandatory since all official communication will take place in this channel.

Slack Group and Channels: this tool enables chatting easily with COVID-X team and with the other COVID-X solutions as well as access discussion channels dedicated to 3 specific topics : business support, technical questions and pilots & ethical aspects. To join the COVID-X Slack groups, access the link that will be shared to you by mail.

COVID-X Team Contact points: If you have any questions, doubts, comments, or suggestions regarding the Acceleration Programme, do not hesitate to **contact your mentors, preferably via the dedicated Slack channel!** Please choose the right mentor according your inquiry:

- **General aspects** - Alberto Sierra Bañón from BOSONIT (alberto.sierra@bosonit.com)
- **Business mentoring** - Justina Ivanova from CIVITTA (justina.ivanova@civitta.com)
- **Technical support** - Sofia Tsekeridou from INTRASOFT (Sofia.TSEKERIDOU@intrasoft-intl.com) and Silvia Uribe from UPM (sum@gatv.ssr.upm.es)
- **Pilots and ethical support** - Giulio Pagliari from HUMANITAS (giulio.pagliari@humanitas.it)
- **Administrative and financial aspects** - Rita Campos from F6S (rita@f6s.com)

For tips & tricks regarding the external communication about your participation, please check the Communication Guidelines from the Annexes.

PARTICIPATION TIMELINE

The funded single and team solutions join the 10-month Programme (November 2021- September 2022) with the following key milestones:

Onboarding phase (November -December 2021)

Once your proposal has been accepted, you will start the onboarding process. The goal of this phase is to prepare the work to be performed during the acceleration programme, including an initial analysis of the business maturity and needs, matchmaking with the appropriate pilot sites and mentors, and the start of the business development roadmap. Three processes need to be carried out in parallel:

- Definition of the KPIs to be used in project monitoring.
- Contract Preparation and signature.
- Acceleration services tailoring.
- Submission of the full ethics application to the relevant Ethical Committee including the study protocol.

During this period, your team must participate online in various mentoring webinars and/or bootcamp as well as in one-to-one meetings with your mentor team.

At the end of this phase, you will be asked to submit the first deliverable of your project:

D1. Experiment KPIs.

Sprint #1 - (January - March 2022)

The project implementation will start in this sprint, and you are required to complete the technical work defined in the work plan provided in your application. The generic goals of Sprint 1 are:

- Complete technical integration with the COVID-X Sandbox.
- Get approval from the Ethical Committee.

During this period, your team participates online in various mentoring webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Moreover, your experiment will be monitored by both clinical (by-weekly basis) and business mentors that will be assigned to your project during the onboarding period. The clinical mentor will be identified within the Healthcare Provider of the Single or Team Solution. Your team will also be matched with a designated business mentor to follow your progress and support your team in the business part of the program.

At the end of this phase (31 March 2022), you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project: **D2 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 1.**

Sprint #2 - (April - June 2022)

You are required to continue with the technical work defined in the work plan provided in your application. The generic goals of the Sprint 2 are:

- Validation of the data model.
- Agreement on IP.

During this period, your team participates in various coaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend the knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training.

Additionally, if the COVID-19 restrictions allow, you may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

At the end of this phase (30 June 2022), you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project: **D3 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 2.**

Sprint #3 - (July - September 2022)

You are required to continue with and finalise the technical work defined in the work plan. The generic goals of the Sprint 3 is:

- Full validation of the product.
- Completion of the feasibility study.

As in the previous sprints, your team must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Additionally, if the COVID-19 restrictions allow, you may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

At the end of this phase (30 September 2022), you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project: **D4 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 3.**

YOUR PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Administrative Documents to be Provided

To finalize the contracting step, we require a set of administrative documents that your team should send through the F6S platform as quickly as possible. In case of questions or doubts, please contact Rita Campos from F6S (rita@f6s.com).

Connect yourself to the F6S platform and consult the list of required documents and information according to your project type:

- **Single Solutions:** www.f6s.com/covid-x-oc2-single-sub-grant-preparation?ref=private
- **Team Solutions:** www.f6s.com/covid-x-oc2-team-sub-grant-preparation?ref=private

Participations

Your team is engaged to join the proposed activities in the framework of the Acceleration Program. All 3 sprints include **webinars, online workshops and other regular meetings** with the mentors. Please notice that in the Sprints 2 and 3, the physical **presence of your team member(s)** might be required for some specific events including the sprint evaluations or events created by the European Commission.

KPIs and Deliverables

By the end of December 2021, your team will set **the key performance indicators (KPIs)** for each Sprint. These KPIs will be defined with the support from your business mentors as these will be validated by the COVID-X team.

These metrics will enable the COVID-X team to track your progress in the Acceleration Program.

To define and to report the KPIs and demonstrate your technical progress, your team will draft and submit 4 deliverables:

Table 1 - Reporting timeline

Deadline	Deliverable
End of December 2021	D1 - KPI Definition
End of March 2022	D2 - Sprint 1 Report
End of June 2022	D3 - Sprint 2 Report
End of September 2022	D4- Sprint 3 Report

Reporting, Evaluations and Payment

COVID-X team focuses on **evaluating the results** (the set KPIs) of your project, the aim is not to monitor the engaged expenditure. The ultimate goal is to boost your solution to the markets as rapidly and strongly as possible to save lives!

Therefore, you are engaged to deliver **the set KPIs and deliverables** during the evaluation phase at the end of each Sprint. Once your report is accepted, we ask you to provide **a financial statement**, and the payment is processed upon the reception of this statement.

All reports will be submitted via the F6S platform (www.f6s.com/covid-x). Moreover, the report templates can be downloaded on the same platform.

Table 2 - Payments timeline

Funding (% of budget)	When (in months)	
10%	January 2022	After approval of the KPIs
30%	April 2022	After evaluation of Sprint 1
30%	July 2022	After evaluation of Sprint 2
30%	October 2022	After evaluation of Sprint 3

Open Access

COVID-X Program follows the open innovation policies recommended by the European Commission. Therefore, all non-confidential documents, essentially related to implemented activities, outcomes & communication, are shared online via Zenodo storage cloud (<https://zenodo.org/>).

The COVID-X website promotes all public outcomes that are relevant for external stakeholders.

ACCELERATION SERVICES

COVID-X Programme provides mentoring with the aim to accelerate the final steps towards the market uptake of the top-rated data solutions. From now on, your team will enter into this programme with the ambition to streamline the deployment and the techno-economic validation of your solution in the fight against COVID-19. To that aim, the COVID-X partners will provide a wide range of free support services based on your identified and concrete needs, including:

- **Financial** - where your experiment will be granted in direct financial support to advance the technology readiness level of your solutions.
- **Technical support** - Online training and inspirational talks in data-driven technologies. Exclusive capacity building service in new technologies, providing support in the use of the data sandbox and the seamless integration and testing of their services with it.
- **Business Mentoring** - including a service portfolio focused on go-to-market strategies in the eHealth sector.
- **Ethical Guidance** - Supporting Tech Companies to get approval from the clinical ethical committees to deploy the solutions in the pilots.

Financial Support

During the programme, each selected team will have access to different amount of funding granted:

- **Single Solution Call:** up to €100,000 maximum granted.
- **Team Solution Call:** up to €150,000 maximum granted per consortium, where the maximum financial contribution to be granted to the beneficiaries shall not exceed the amount of €100.000 for SMEs and €50.000 for Healthcare providers.

Technical Support Services

- **Capacity building in new technologies:** A set of available technology courses will be provided by **BOSONIT** experts using an online tool to facilitate access. These courses will be tailor-made to the needs of the selected experiments and will address the main technology areas applied by them.

The total number of courses to be provided is 3 (1 per sprint). Final topics will be defined within the onboarding calls and can include areas such as Data Science, Big Data, RPA, Python, AI, Cybersecurity...

Courses will be delivered online, via Zoom and will have a duration of **8 hours each**. At the end of the courses, participants will be evaluated and will be able to receive a COVID-X Certificate.

- **Sandbox training and support:** Presentation and discussion of the technologies, methodologies and approaches with respect to the deployment and integration of Sandbox related applications. **UPM** and **INTRASOFT** lead these training parts.

Planned and ad-hoc online discussions highlighting aspects of the containerisation and deployment of apps interacting with the sandbox. Explanation of the offered tools, APIs and ways of engaging with available data. Walkaround the UI components of the platform and related dashboards with introductory information on how to use them. Technical information for API interaction.

This service will be provided on a general basis to all the third parties during the onboarding phase and will be followed up during the mentoring sessions. Individual 1-to-1 mentoring on the Sandbox will be provided if necessary.

Business Support Services

- **Mentoring programme:** Mentoring will give you access to specialised expert knowledge that in standard acceleration mostly is unavailable. Experienced experts will provide strategic overview on different topics and provide both business mentoring insights and strategy. The business acceleration programme will cover 8 different business-related topics in general sessions (approx. duration of 1-hour + Q&A) and will be delivered on a monthly-basis. In addition, each topic-specific mentor from a related industry will provide individual consultation sessions for each team after the general sessions have taken place to advise on specific questions and/or concerns that may have arisen.

After the webinars, all the participants will be asked to put in practice the learnings and tasks will be assigned. **CIVITTA** will provide materials and guidelines on how to complete these tasks.

Each team will also be matched with a general business mentor. These mentors will follow the progress of the team, be available for personal consultations and any business related questions or help that might be needed for the participants.

The aim of the mentoring is to create individual business development roadmaps that will be provided at the end of the Covid-X Programme. **CIVITTA will also leverage its pool of knowledgeable business mentors who will be matched on an ad-hoc basis with the teams to support them in tackling more specific business-related topics.**

- **Progress reviews:** will be organised during each Sprint. It will gather the project teams, together with consortium partners and other relevant stakeholders to assess and share the main experiences, problems. It will also give the possibility to work with each other and increase the impact and awareness of different COVID-X solutions.
- **Mentoring Workshops:** will be thematic and will be categorised in three main topics: Technical, Clinical and Business.
- **Inspirational talks:** Top-notch technical and business experts will host a set of talks. These talks will cover online chats with speakers giving insights about the COVID-19 pandemic & about the start-ups scene around it, including officials from the European Commission (EC) and even showcasing COVID-X solutions. At least 3 inspirational talks per Sprint will be set up making use of online live transmission.

- **Business development roadmap:** in accordance with the mentoring action plan, this will be drawn up and delivered at the end of Sprint 3. This will be a live-document that identifies the stages of business and technology development needed to be accomplished during the Acceleration Programme.
- **Demo moments and Success stories:** COVID-X Program will publicly share the Acceleration Program impact on the project website (www.covid-x.eu) and social media (Twitter & LinkedIn). To collect the stories, the founders will be interviewed, and they fill in an online survey / or in a short video. The major outcomes of each funded project, ie. their success story, will be drafted in a short & defined format (following the visual COVID-X brand) during the Sprint 3. Moreover, a promotional video will be produced with video interviews of several participants explaining their solution (objective, status & market perspectives) , and the impact of the COVID-X Program on their project.

PILOTS & RESEARCH PROTOCOL

COVID-X partners will facilitate and create the conditions and environment required by each of the beneficiaries' pilots, either by partner hospitals (ICH, SERMAS, KI) or by the onboarded external healthcare partners for the Team Solutions.

The Consortium will help Single and Team solutions in maximizing the impact of the pilots and contribute to the testing and deployment operations as well as market uptake of mature health technologies for the prevention and optimised treatment of the COVID-19 disease.

All pilots will be conducted and monitored with the aim of ensuring a high clinical impact in terms of effectiveness, reliability, quality, precision, accuracy and rapid response of the tested solutions to overcome the state-of-art achieving better outcomes for patients avoiding overtreatment and under-treatment conditions.

As a reminder, the clinical partners of the COVID-X Team will pursue the following scopes within the project:

- **Istituto Clinico Humanitas (ICH, Italy)** expects to have collaboration with entities to create and validate novel AI-based models with high accuracy for a fast CT / X-RAY scan analysis aiming at supporting the diagnosis of COVID-19 via classification and estimation of the degree of affection. Moreover, this site is interested in development of AI-based solutions for cross analysis between clinical and radiological available data to assess personalized clinical paths and treatment to improve clinical response of classified patients.
- **Hospital Clinico San Carlos (SERMAS, Spain)** expects to have collaboration with entities providing solutions, swiftly and precisely diagnose this condition and assess its prognosis. In particular, the hospital is interested in identifying “exceptions to the rule”; i.e. subjects belonging to risk groups but who will fully recover with no or minor complications, and vice versa.
- **Karolinska Institutet (KI, Sweden)** is interested in piloting solutions that enhance the data collection from patients with potential COVID-19 diagnosis, meaning improving the pre-diagnostic processes and clinical pathways with AI based developed components.

The support for the SMEs participating in the pilots will involve **following cross-collaboration activities** between their single solution team and the appointed pilot sites / with the Team solution team including their healthcare partner:

- **Analysis of feasibility of the solution proposed** – through the definition of a GANTT for goals, KPIs and monitoring the progress of each task.
- **Ethical committee approval for each pilot/solution** – before accessing clinical data and starting the validation phase, each Single or Team solution should get the approval of the local Ethical Committee to ensure that the submitted proposals are compliant with the current legal and ethical regulations.
- **Access to data for third parties** – integration with the Covid-X Sandbox and definition of the dataset that the Single or Team solution will need in order to validate the solution.

- **Deployment and testing** – through the usage of the Covid-X Sandbox, each Single or Team solution will be able to proceed with the validation of the solution and the accomplishment of the agreed goals.
- **Regular review/monitoring meetings** – during the pilot, Single and Team solutions will be monitored in order to guarantee the success of the project and discuss the best ways to validate the solutions. Participants will take part in Experiment Progress Meetings (EPs) every two weeks and they will discuss with the clinical mentor the stage of each KPI and identify the new tasks to perform.

Research Protocol

Usually, Clinical partners require the definition of a research protocol and the approval of a local Ethical Committee before starting a research together with a third party. Specifically, the research protocol is a document that describes the project and the basis on which the Ethical Committee verifies the ethical and formal compliance and feasibility.

Since the approval procedure of the research protocol is a crucial step for the beginning of the validation of Single or Team solutions, below we give further information regarding a potential pipeline. In many cases the Ethical Committee is an independent body and its procedures and regulations may vary depending on the pilot site. Each Clinical Partner will be in charge to give details on timing, documentation and procedures related to the submission of the research protocol.

In case of Team solutions and if required, the external beneficiary Hospital or Clinic should give the same type of information and support regarding the submission of the research protocol to their Ethical Committee.

As reported in the Section 9.1.2 of the OC# 2 Guidelines for Applicants, all the selected Single and Team solutions should get the approval from the Ethical Committee within the end of Sprint 1. Since this process may take up to two months, please start working on the Research Protocol together with the Clinical Partner as soon as possible.

High-level structure of a Research Protocol

This document consists of different sections describing the goals and the design of the pilot project. Usually, the following sections should be filled in:

- Name of the project and main responsible/PI;
- Abstract and rationale of the pilot study;
- Design of the pilot;
- Expected results and timeline;
- Annexes may be requested depending on the local regulations and procedures (e.g. Sub-grant Agreement, etc.).

The approval of the Ethical Committee might be a mandatory document to kickoff the pilot implementation. For this reason, it is crucial to work on the research protocol from the very beginning of your participation in COVID-X. Moreover, the involved clinical partners not only should offer SMEs guidance through the procedures and documentation, but should give support regarding contents and deadlines.

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Communicate and share your participation in the COVID-X as much as possible in the dedicated channels!

Please remember that Beneficiaries of any EU funding are engaged to acknowledge the support from the **European Commission**, which means using the acknowledgement of EU funding on your website, flyers or other related promotional material. To support this, you can find our [Communication Guidelines](#) in the Annex.

- Website www.covid-x.eu
- LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/
- Facebook www.facebook.com/TheCovidX
- Twitter [@TheCovidX](https://twitter.com/TheCovidX)

COVID-X PARTNERS & TEAM

Before the bootcamp, we would like to introduce you to the key COVID-X team that manages the Acceleration Program, the project communication and supports your solution to save lives faster. **Happy to meet you!**

F6S

COVID-X Coordinator & Open Call Manager

Rita Campos
Project Coordinator

Diana Guardado
Innovation Projects
Manager

Antonio Damasceno
Project Coordinator

Hugo Cantao
Financial Manager

AUSTRALO

Communication and Community

Mona Marill
Project Manager

Giulia Pastor
Project Manager

Blanca Arregui
Communication
Manager

CIVITTA

CIVITTA
Go-to-market Acceleration Manager

Ronalds Strauhs
Project Manager

Justina Ivanova
Senior Consultant

Kristaps Budrevics
Consultant

BOSONIT
Technical Acceleration Manager

Alberto Sierra
Senior Innovation
Expert

Paula Ciaurriz
Innovation Consultant

INTRASOFT

Data integration & management, Data visualization, Sandbox integration

Sofia Tsekeridou
Senior Research and
Innovation Manager -
Expert,
Head of Security &
Safety Lab

**Themistoklis
Anagnostopoulos**
Senior Software
Engineer

Serafeim Tsironis
Senior Research &
Development
Engineer

**Filoipimin
Lykokanellos**
Senior Software
Engineer

EIGHT BELLS

Data protection & security, Sandbox design

Despoina Gkatzioura
Software Engineer and
Project Consultant

Theodora Kousta
Project Consultant

POLITÉCNICA

Universidad Politecnica Madrid

AI and federated learning, Third parties integration

Frederico Alvarez
Professor and GATV
(UPM) Director

Borja Arroyo
Software Engineer

Javier Serrano
Researcher &
Project Manager

Silvia Uribe
assistant professor

Humanitas Mirasole Clinical Partner Italy

Giovanni Angelotti
Lead Data Scientist,
Humanitas AI Center

Carlotta Cattaneo
Head of Business Innovation
& AI,
Humanitas AI Center

Giulio Pagliari
Project Manager,
Humanitas AI Center

Servicio Madrileño de Salud
Clinical Partner Spain

Luis Rodriguez-Rodriguez
Senior Researcher

José Manuel Laperal
Information Security Manager

Elena Arredondo
Innovation Manager

Karolinska Institute
Clinical Partner Sweden

Carl-Johan Sundberg
Professor

Sabine Koch
Professor

Sokratis Nifakos
PhD Student

COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

This document gives the key guidelines for both internal and external communication activities related to COVID-X Programme. All beneficiaries of the Programme should use the created tools for communication including dedicated communication channels & messages as well as the COVID-X branding.

COVID-X in a nutshell

The following text is a short description of the COVID-X Project's objectives and actions. It can be used in different contexts: emails, presentations, social media posts, etc.

COVID-X Programme is a European innovation initiative offering access to funding and to a tailored **acceleration programme** for start-ups and companies. The objective is to **boost the market uptake** of AI and data solutions [at TRL7+] to defeat COVID-19 and to save lives. It is supported by the European Commission as part of the response plan to **defeat COVID-19 through the power of data**.

Through two Open Calls, COVID-X grants 30+ selected companies: **[Single Players]** obtain **100K€ in equity-free funding** and get access in **technical, business and ethical mentoring** as well as in **clinical validation** at one of the COVID-X pilot sites (in Italy, Spain or Sweden). If the company brings in a Healthcare Provider that can validate their solution, the financial support will go up to **150K€ [Team Players]**. All selected solutions address challenges related to **diagnosis, prognosis or follow-up of COVID-19 patients**.

For more information: www.covid-x.eu

Internal Communication

All internal communication takes place in two dedicated channels:

- **Mailing list:** covid-x-oc2-solutions@f6s.com - subscription to the mailing list is mandatory since all official communication will take place in this channel.
- **Slack Group and channels:** this tool enables chatting easily with COVID-X team and with the other COVID-X solutions as well. Once you receive the email to join the team work

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space, you will find the general channel and the channels dedicated to 3 specific topics: business support, technical questions and pilots & ethical aspects.

COVID-X Team Contact points: If you have any questions, doubts, comments or suggestions regarding the Acceleration Programme, do not hesitate to **contact your mentors!** Please choose the right mentor according to your inquiry:

- **General aspects** - Alberto Sierra Bañón from BOSONIT (alberto.sierra@bosonit.com)
- **Business mentoring** - Justina Ivanova from CIVITTA (justina.ivanova@civitta.com)
- **Technical support** - Sofia Tsekeridou from INTRASOFT (Sofia.TSEKERIDOU@intrasoft-intl.com) and Silvia Uribe from UPM (sum@gatv.ssr.upm.es)
- **Pilots and ethical support** - Giulio Pagliari from HUMANITAS (giulio.pagliari@humanitas.it)
- **Administrative and financial aspects** - Rita Campos from F6S (rita@f6s.com)

Branding

The COVID-X branding includes the fonts, colours, logos and banners that should be used in all COVID-X-related communication.

Project name

COVID-X should be written in capitals and with a hyphen between the D and the X.

The full name is **COVID-X Programme** including the Acceleration Programme and access to direct funding.

Font types

Saira: Use in **titles** - download it [here](#).

Abel: Use in **body text** - download it [here](#).

Colour palette

Use colours from the dedicated palette:

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Logo

Please find the **logo** available in this link : https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_logo

If your company wants to add the COVID-X logo to the website, please **link the logo** to the COVID-X website.

Banners

Find the **main banner** available : https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Main_banner

Leaflet

Please find the one-pager here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Leaflet. This leaflet gives a general overview of the programme and it can be freely used for all COVID-X related communication.

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COVID-X Website - www.covid-x.eu

The project website

- Gives a general overview of the Program.
- Promotes the open calls and their outcomes.
- Shares updates about COVID-X achievements, including news from solutions.
- Promotes the COVID-X Community (ie. the funded teams & solutions) towards external stakeholders.

COVID-X team highly recommends promoting the project website as often as possible (in any presentation, social media posts, newsletters, blog posts ,etc.).

Social Media

If your company & team have social media channels, please kindly follow the COVID-X profiles you find below.

When you want to post information about the project on social media, remember to tag COVID-X accounts and also that it is important to talk about it in a concise, informal and positive way, engagingly, and use hashtags where possible in clear and simple language. Innovative and different. Speak personally.

Hashtags to be used: **#TheCovidX, #GameOn, #DatavsCovid, #GameChangers**

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/TheCovidX>

Facebook: www.facebook.com/TheCovidX

Linkedin: www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/

YouTube: www.youtube.com/channel/UCZg26pyMWfEUfJiulukh-Ig

Please find some graphics for posting on social media:

- Linkedin & Facebook graphic is available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_GameChanger_FBAndLK

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- Twitter graphic is available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_GameChanger_Twitter

Success Stories

During the programme you will be requested to contribute to a success story, summarising your COVID-X experience at the different phases.

You will be contacted by the Communication Manager sharing with you the main points to be addressed in your post. Moreover, all success stories shall be shared on public communication channels of the project, which enables to showcase **the COVID-X impact**.

Media Appearance & Follow-Up

During your participation in COVID-X Programme, **if your solution, team or company achieves any media appearance** (e.g. in social media, newspapers, newsletters, etc), please share this update with the COVID-X Communication Manager so that the COVID-X can leverage this achievement in related activities.

Participation in Videos

During your COVID-X participation, your team can be asked to participate in a video with the goal to share publicly the COVID-X Program achievements. Your participation will be confirmed in advantage with the image rights agreement.

Produced video(s) shall be published on the COVID-X website and on the COVID-X YouTube channel. All participants can freely use it for their marketing activities.

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Events

If & when your company participates in an event/conference/workshop, etc. and you present/promote your participation in COVID-X project, we would kindly ask you to:

BEFORE THE EVENT

1. Inform the communication manager
2. Use the acknowledgement stated below for announcing your participation in the event.

DURING THE EVENT

3. Tweet and mention [@TheCovidX](#)
4. In case you do not have a Twitter account, you should send the text you want to be published on Twitter and some pictures to COVID-X Communication Manager (*see below*)

AFTER THE EVENT

5. Prepare a short written description summarizing your participation in the event.
6. Send the text to the communication manager who will take care of publishing it on the COVID-X website.

Press Release

The COVID-X team issues new press releases as soon as new milestones are met, such as all the solutions are successfully onboarded in the Acceleration Programme. All new PRs will be shared with you.

Please find the latest PR here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_PR_Nov2021

Newsletters

In case your company is going to release any newsletter including information about COVID-X, please share it with us! If you need any graphic or textual input to be used in the newsletter, please contact the COVID-X Communication Manager.

EU logo, acknowledgement and disclaimer

Beneficiaries of any EU funding are engaged to acknowledge the support of the European Commission; this is a contractual part of your funding agreement. Please use the acknowledgement template below for your website. It should be visible (preferably on the main page) at least during the contract period.

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COVID-X Communication Manager

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To share your communication updates and to address any question or doubts about the outreach activities or guidelines contact **COVID-X Communication Manager: Blanca Arregui (AUSTRALO)** - blanca@australo.org

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